

Graphical Abstract

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Highlights

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- Interpretable anomaly detector with self-supervised adaptation
- Demonstrates interpretability by providing dynamic operating limits
- Leverages self-learning approach on streamed IoT data
- Utilizes existing SCADA-based industrial infrastructure
- Offers faster response time to incidents due to root cause isolation

Adaptable and Interpretable Framework for Anomaly Detection in SCADA-based Industrial Systems

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce an Adaptable and Interpretable Framework for Anomaly Detection (AID) designed for industrial systems utilizing IoT data streams on top of well-established SCADA systems. AID leverages dynamic conditional probability distribution modeling to capture the normal operation of dynamic systems and isolate the root causes of anomalies at the level of individual inputs. The self-supervised framework dynamically updates parameters of underlying model, allowing it to adapt to non-stationarity. AID interprets anomalies as significant deviations from conditional probability, encompassing interactions as well as both spatial and temporal irregularities by exposing them as features. Crucially, AID provides dynamic operating limits to integrate with existing alarm handling mechanisms in SCADA-based IoT systems. Two industrial-scale case studies demonstrate AID's capabilities. The first study showcases AID's effectiveness on energy storage system, adapting to changes, setting context-aware limits for SCADA, and ability to leverage a physics-based model. The second study monitors battery module temperatures, where AID identifies hardware faults, emphasizing its relevance to energy storage safety. A benchmark evaluation on real data shows that AID delivers comparable performance to other self-learning adaptable anomaly detection methods, with the significant advancement in diagnostic capabilities for improved system reliability and performance.

Keywords: Anomaly detection, Root cause isolation, Iterative learning, Statistical learning, Self-supervised learning

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1. Introduction

2 Anomaly detection systems play a critical role in risk-averse systems by
3 identifying abnormal patterns and adapting to novel expected patterns in
4 data. These systems are particularly vital in the context of Internet of Things
5 (IoT) devices that continuously stream high-fidelity data to control units.

6 In this rapidly evolving field with long-spanning roots, Chandola et al.
7 (2009) conducted an influential review of prior research efforts across diverse
8 application domains. Recent studies have underscored the need for holistic
9 and tunable anomaly detection methods accessible to operators (Laptev
10 et al., 2015; Kejariwal, 2015; Cook et al., 2020).

11 Cook et al. denote substantial aspects that pose challenges to anomaly
12 detection in IoT, including the temporal, spatial, and external context of
13 measurements, multivariate characteristics, noise, and nonstationarity (Cook
14 et al., 2020). To address these complexity issues, Zhang et al. (2024) have
15 successfully employed spatially distributed sensors and time-relative modu-
16 lation. Their approach has proven effective, particularly in the context of
17 complex non-linear systems, offering potential solutions to some of the chal-
18 lenges posed by IoT data. Huang et al., on the other hand, tackled the
19 problems of detecting global outliers, local outliers, and outlier clusters si-
20 multaneously. Their proposed approach, based on density estimation, relies
21 on the notion that density distributions should exhibit minimal variations
22 in local areas. To achieve this, they introduce a novel turning ratio metric,
23 which reduces reliance on hyperparameters and enhances anomaly detection
24 (Huang et al., 2023).

25 Additionally, feature engineering techniques play a crucial role in cap-
26 turing contextual properties and enhancing anomaly detection performance
27 (Fan et al., 2019). However, it is worth noting that feature engineering
28 may introduce categorical variables and significantly increase the dimension-
29 ality of the data, requiring specific methods for handling large data, size-
30 able data storage, and substantial computational resources (Talagala et al.,
31 2021). Recently, Li et al. introduced an attribute-weighted outlier detection
32 algorithm, designed for high-dimensional datasets with mixtures of categor-
33 ical and numerical data. Their approach assigns different weights to indi-
34 vidual attributes based on their importance in anomaly detection and uses
35 these weights to calculate distances between data points. Notably, Li et

36 al. demonstrated the superior performance of their algorithm compared to
37 state-of-the-art methods (Li and Liu, 2024). Another strategy for handling
38 high-dimensional data involves using deep learning methods with synthetic
39 normal data to enhance the detection of outliers with subtle deviations, as
40 proposed in Du et al. (2024).

41 Nevertheless, the presence of nonstationarity, often stemming from con-
42 cept drift (a shift in data patterns due to changes in statistical distribution)
43 and change points (permanent alterations in system state), presents a sub-
44 stantial challenge (Salehi and Rashidi, 2018). In practical scenarios, those
45 changes tend to be unpredictable in both their spatial and temporal aspects.
46 Consequently, they require systems with solid outlier rejection capabilities of
47 intelligent tracking algorithms (Barbosa Roa et al., 2019). This underscores
48 the critical importance of an anomaly detection method’s ability to adapt to
49 evolving data structures, especially in long-term deployments. Nevertheless,
50 as (Tartakovsky et al., 2013) remarked, immediate detection is not a feasible
51 option unless there is a high tolerance for false alarms. Promising balance
52 between early transition detection and low false alarm rate could be achieved
53 by contrastive learning approach. Deldari et al. (2021) have shown that by
54 evaluating cosine similarity between predicted future representation and an-
55 ticipated representation of time windows, it is possible to detect evolution in
56 data with high accuracy.

57 The adaptation of batch models at scale introduces a significant latency
58 in detector adaptation (Wu et al., 2021). Incremental learning methods al-
59 lowed adaptation while restraining the storage of the whole dataset. The su-
60 pervised operator-in-the-loop solution offered by Pannu et al. (2012) showed
61 the detector’s adaptation to data labeled on the flight. Others approached
62 the problem as sequential processing of bounded data buffers in univariate
63 signals (Ahmad et al., 2017) and multivariate systems (Bosman et al., 2015).

64 *1.1. Related Work*

65 Recent advances in anomaly detection have broadened its scope to in-
66 clude root cause identification governed by the development of explanatory
67 methods capable of diagnosing and tracking faults across the system. Stud-
68 ies can be split into two groups of distinct approaches. The first group
69 approaches explainability as the importance of individual features (Carletti
70 et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2019; Amarasinghe et al., 2018). Those studies
71 allow an explanation of novelty by considering features independently. The

72 second group uses statistical learning creating models explainable via prob-
73 ability. For instance, the integration of variational Bayesian inference prob-
74 abilistic graph neural network allowed Zhang et al. to model the posterior
75 distribution of sensor dependency for gas leakage localization on unlabeled
76 data (Zhang et al., 2023b). Yang et al. recently proposed a Bayesian net-
77 work (BN) for fault detection and diagnosis. In this BN, individual nodes
78 of the network represent normally distributed variables, whereas the multi-
79 ple regression model defines weights and relationships. Using the predefined
80 structure of the BN, the authors propose offline training with online detection
81 and diagnosis (Yang et al., 2022).

82 Given the infrequent occurrence of anomalies and their potential absence
83 in training data, the incorporation of synthetic data or feature extraction
84 for various detected events emerges to assist diagnosis of the system. Brito
85 et al. designed synthetic faults based on expert knowledge and introduced
86 them into a transfer learning classifier to exploit faults in rotating machinery,
87 with a subsequent explanation layer (Brito et al., 2023). Conversely, We et al.
88 leveraged feature selection to expose various types of abnormal behavior. The
89 team presents competitive performance while using change in relationships
90 to provide causal inference (Wu et al., 2024).

91 However, it is crucial to underscore that offline training, as previously em-
92 phasized, is inherently inadequate when it comes to adapting to anticipated
93 novel patterns, rendering it unsuitable for sustained, long-term operation on
94 IoT devices.

95 This paper emphasizes the importance of combining adaptability in in-
96 terpretable anomaly detection and proposes a method that addresses this
97 challenge in real industrial systems. Here we report the discovery and char-
98 acterization of an adaptive anomaly detection method for existing supervi-
99 sory control and data acquisition (SCADA) systems, employing streaming
100 IoT data. The ability to diagnose multivariate data while providing root
101 cause isolation via statistical learning, extends our previous contribution to
102 the field as presented in (Wadinger and Kvasnica, 2023). The proposed algo-
103 rithm aims to represent a general method that aids a range of existing safety-
104 critical systems where anomaly diagnosis and identification are paramount.
105 The schematic overview of the proposed method’s integration is presented in
106 Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the proposed method AID.

107 *1.2. Novelty of proposed approach*

108 The idea of using statistical outlier detection is well-established. We
 109 highlight the impactful contributions of Yamanishi et al. in (Yamanishi and
 110 Takeuchi, 2002; Yamanishi et al., 2004). The authors propose a method
 111 for detecting anomalies in a time series. The method is based on the as-
 112 sumption that the continuous data is generated by a mixture of Gaussian
 113 distributions, while discrete data is modeled as histogram density. The au-
 114 thors solve the problem of change point detection as well. However, the
 115 adaptation system is unaware of such changes, making the moving window
 116 the only source of adaptation. Online vectorized forecasting methods based
 117 on well-established autoregression and moving averages have recently shown
 118 the capability of adapting to non-stationarity in multivariate systems with-
 119 out supervision Melnyk et al. (2016); Zhang et al. (2023a). Their extension
 120 to diagnostic tasks is yet to be explored. Our self-supervised approach facil-
 121 itates intelligent adaptation concerning detected change points, to increase
 122 the speed of adaptation where the probability of concept drift is high. By
 123 leveraging its ability to adapt to changes in operational states, our proposed
 124 method operates autonomously when such changes occur. Moreover, Yaman-
 125 ishi et al. (2004) does not attempt to isolate the root cause of the anomaly.
 126 Our approach extends statistical outlier detection by incorporating inter-
 127 pretability. This is achieved by evaluating the inverse cumulative distribu-
 128 tion function of the latest conditional probabilities for each measurement,
 129 considering the remainder of the measurements, and establishing limits that
 130 define the threshold for normal event probabilities.

131 A limited number of studies have focused on adaptation and interpretabil-
 132 ity within the framework of anomaly detection. Two recent contributions in

133 this area are made by Steenwinckel et al. as reported in (Steenwinckel, 2018;
134 Steenwinckel et al., 2021). In Steenwinckel (2018), the authors emphasize
135 the importance of combining prior knowledge with a data-driven approach
136 to achieve interpretability, particularly concerning root cause isolation. They
137 propose a novel approach that involves extracting features based on knowl-
138 edge graph pattern extraction and integrating them into the anomaly de-
139 tection mechanism. This graph is subsequently transformed into a matrix,
140 and adaptive region-of-interest extraction is performed using reinforcement
141 learning techniques. To enhance interpretability, a Generative Adversarial
142 Network (GAN) reconstructs a new graphical representation based on se-
143 lected vectors. However, it is important to note that the validation of this
144 idealized approach is pending further investigation. Lately, Steenwinckel
145 et al. (2021) introduced a comprehensive framework for adaptive anomaly
146 detection and root cause analysis in data streams. While the adaptation
147 process is driven by user feedback, the specific mechanism remains undis-
148 closed. The authors present an interpretation of their method through a user
149 dashboard, featuring visualizations of raw data. This dashboard is capable of
150 distinguishing between track-related problems and train-related issues, based
151 on whether multiple trains at the same geographical location approach the
152 anomaly. Meanwhile, our efforts are directed towards the development of a
153 self-supervised method that can learn autonomously, reducing the reliance on
154 human supervision, which is often constrained by time limitations and can
155 lead to significant delays in adaptation. Our method is distinguished by its
156 straightforward statistical reasoning and the ability to isolate the root cause
157 of anomalies. The interpretability of our method is demonstrated through
158 the establishment of dynamic operating limits for each signal, leveraging con-
159 ditional probabilities derived from the signal and other system measurements
160 and features. This provides operators with a clear understanding of the sys-
161 tem’s state and the underlying causes of anomalies and offers interoperability
162 with existing alarm handling mechanisms in SCADA which utilize operating
163 limits. To the best of our knowledge, this study appears to be one of the ini-
164 tial attempts to introduce a self-supervised approach for adaptive anomaly
165 detection and root cause isolation in SCADA-based systems utilizing IoT
166 data streams.

167 *1.3. Validation*

168 Two real-world industrial-scale case studies showcase that our proposed
169 method has the capacity to explain anomalies, isolate the root cause, and

170 allow adaptation to change points, allowing long-term deployment at the
171 end users of energy storage systems. We observe similar detection perfor-
172 mance, albeit with lower scalability, on benchmark data when comparing
173 our approach to well-established unsupervised anomaly detection methods
174 in streamed data which create a bedrock for many state-of-the-art contribu-
175 tions, such as One-Class SVM (Amer et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2014; Krawczyk
176 and Woźniak, 2015; Miao et al., 2019; Gözüaçık and Can, 2021), and Half-
177 Space Trees (Wetzig et al., 2019; Lyu et al., 2020).

178 *1.4. Practical Impact*

179 Potential applications of the proposed method are in the field of energy
180 storage systems, where the ability to detect anomalies and isolate their root
181 causes while adapting to changes in operation and environment, is crucial
182 for the system safety. The proposed method is designed to be integrated
183 into the existing infrastructure of the systems, utilizing IoT data streams on
184 top of well-established SCADA systems. SCADA systems continuously mon-
185 itor these process data in real-time, embodying alarm handling mechanisms,
186 which are designed to notify operators of the system’s abnormal behavior
187 and drive attention to the root of the problem. By comparing the current
188 values to the upper and lower operating limits, they take action when a vari-
189 able exceeds or falls below these limits. However, safe operating limits are
190 often established based on a combination of equipment design limits and the
191 dynamics of the process (Stauffer and Chastain-Knight, 2021). Those are
192 indifferent to the actual state of the system and environmental conditions.
193 The proposed method allows the establishment of dynamic operating limits,
194 based on the current state of the system and its environment, with direct uti-
195 lization in SCADA systems expecting minimal intervention to existing infras-
196 tructure. This allows the system to operate closer or further from its design
197 limits, increasing its safety and profitability. The dynamic operating limits
198 allow operational metrics monitoring, making potential early detection and
199 prevention easier. Using general adaptable methods without interpretability,
200 on the other hand, may pose safety risks and lower total financial benefits,
201 as the triggered false alarms may need to be thoroughly analyzed, resulting
202 in prolonged downtimes.

203 The main contribution of the proposed solution to the developed body of
204 research is that it:

- 205 • Interpretable anomaly detector with self-supervised adaptation

- 206 • Demonstrates interpretability by providing dynamic operating limits
- 207 • Leverages self-learning approach on streamed IoT data
- 208 • Utilizes existing SCADA-based industrial infrastructure
- 209 • Offers faster response time to incidents due to root cause isolation

210 1.5. Paper Organization

211 The rest of the paper is structured as follows: We begin with the problem
 212 and motivation in **Section 1**, providing context. Next, in **Section 2**, we
 213 lay the theoretical groundwork. Our proposed adaptive anomaly detection
 214 method is detailed in **Section 3**. We then demonstrate real-world industrial-
 215 scale applications in **Section 4**. Finally, we conclude the paper in **Section 5**,
 216 summarizing findings and discussing future research directions.

217 2. Preliminaries

218 In this section, we present the fundamental ideas that form the basis
 219 of the developed approach. Subsection 2.1 explains Welford’s online algo-
 220 rithm, which can adjust distribution to changes in real-time. Subsection 2.2
 221 proposes a two-pass implementation that can reverse the impact of expired
 222 samples. The math behind distribution modeling in Subsection 2.3 estab-
 223 lishes the foundation for the Gaussian anomaly detection model discussed in
 224 Subsection 2.5, followed by conditional probability computation in Subsec-
 225 tion 2.4. The last subsection of the preliminaries is devoted to the definition
 226 of anomalies.

227 2.1. Welford’s Online Algorithm

228 Welford introduced a numerically stable online algorithm for calculating
 229 mean and variance in a single pass through data. Therefore, the algorithm
 230 allows the processing of IoT device measurements without the need to store
 231 their values (Welford, 1962).

232 Given measurement x_i where $i = 1, \dots, n$ is a sample index in sample
 233 population n , the corrected sum of squares S_n is defined as

$$S_n = \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x}_n)^2, \quad (1)$$

234 with the running mean \bar{x}_n defined as previous mean \bar{x}_{n-1} weighted by pro-
 235 portion of previously seen population $n - 1$ corrected by current sample as

$$\bar{x}_n = \frac{n-1}{n}\bar{x}_{n-1} + \frac{1}{n}x_n = \bar{x}_{n-1} + \frac{x_n - \bar{x}_{n-1}}{n}. \quad (2)$$

236 Throughout this paper, we consider the following formulation of an update
 237 to the corrected sum of squares:

$$S_n = S_{n-1} + (x_n - \bar{x}_{n-1})(x_n - \bar{x}_n), \quad (3)$$

238 as it is less prone to numerical instability due to catastrophic cancellation,
 239 significant loss of precision due to subtracting two nearly equal numbers.
 240 Finally, the corresponding unbiased variance is

$$s_n^2 = \frac{S_n}{n-1}. \quad (4)$$

241 This implementation of the Welford method requires the storage of three
 242 scalars: \bar{x}_{n-1} ; n ; S_n .

243 2.2. Inverting Welford's Algorithm

244 Based on (2), it is clear that the influence of the latest sample over the
 245 running mean decreases as the population n grows. For this reason, regulat-
 246 ing the number of samples used for sample mean and variance computation
 247 has crucial importance over adaptation. Given access to the instances used
 248 for computation and expiration period $t_e \in \mathbb{N}_0^{n-1}$, reverting the impact of
 249 x_{n-t_e} can be written as follows

$$S_{n-1} = S_n - (x_{n-t_e} - \bar{x}_{n-1})(x_{n-t_e} - \bar{x}_n), \quad (5)$$

250 where the reverted mean is given as

$$\bar{x}_{n-1} = \frac{n}{n-1}\bar{x}_n - \frac{1}{n-1}x_{n-t_e} = \bar{x}_n - \frac{x_{n-t_e} - \bar{x}_n}{n-1}. \quad (6)$$

251 Finally, the unbiased variance follows the formula:

$$s_{n-1}^2 = \frac{S_{n-1}}{n-2}. \quad (7)$$

252 Notably, inversion allows the algorithm to keep a constant rate of adap-
 253 tation at the cost of storing a bounded data buffer.

254 *2.3. Statistical Model of Multivariate System*

255 Multivariate normal distribution generalizes the multivariate systems to
 256 the model where the degree to which variables are related is represented by
 257 the covariance matrix. Gaussian normal distribution of variables is a reason-
 258 able assumption for process measurements, as it is a common distribution
 259 that arises from stable physical processes measured with noise (Mishra and
 260 Datta-Gupta, 2018). The general notation of multivariate normal distribu-
 261 tion is:

$$\mathbf{X} \sim \mathcal{N}_k(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}), \quad (8)$$

262 where k -dimensional mean vector is denoted as $\boldsymbol{\mu} = (\bar{x}_1, \dots, \bar{x}_k)^T \in \mathbb{R}^k$
 263 and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k}$ is the $k \times k$ covariance matrix, where k is the index of last
 264 random variable.

265 The probability density function (PDF) $f(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$ of multivariate normal
 266 distribution is denoted as:

$$f(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{k/2} |\boldsymbol{\Sigma}|^{1/2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x}-\boldsymbol{\mu})^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}-\boldsymbol{\mu})}, \quad (9)$$

267 where \mathbf{x} is a k -dimensional vector of measurements x_i at time i , $|\boldsymbol{\Sigma}|$
 268 denotes the determinant of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$, and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}$ is the inverse of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$.

269 The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of a multivariate Gaussian
 270 distribution describes the probability that all components of the random
 271 vector \mathbf{X} take on a value less than or equal to a particular point q in space,
 272 and can be used to evaluate the likelihood of observing a particular set of
 273 measurements or data points. In other words, it gives the probability of
 274 observing a random vector that falls within a certain region of space. The
 275 standard notation of CDF is as follows:

$$F(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) = \int_{-\infty}^q f(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) d\mathbf{x}, \quad (10)$$

276 where $d\mathbf{x}$ denotes the integration over all k dimensions of \mathbf{x} .

277 As the equation (10) cannot be integrated explicitly, an algorithm for
 278 numerical computation was proposed in Genz (2000).

279 Given the PDF, we can also determine the value of \mathbf{x} that corresponds to a
 280 given quantile q using a numerical method for inversion of CDF (ICDF) often
 281 denoted as percent point function (PPF) or $F(\mathbf{x}; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})^{-1}$. An algorithm that
 282 calculates the value of the PPF is part of standard statistical software tools.

283 *2.4. Conditional Probability Distribution*

284 Considering that we observe particular vector \mathbf{x}_i , we can update probabil-
 285 ity distributions, calculated according to the rules of conditional probability,
 286 of individual measurements within the vector given the rest of the measure-
 287 ments in \mathbf{x}_i . Let's assume multivariate normal distribution (8) and without
 288 loss of generality, that the vector \mathbf{x}_i can be partitioned into subset variable
 289 x_a , and complement vector \mathbf{x}_b as follows

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \begin{bmatrix} x_a \\ \mathbf{x}_b \end{bmatrix} \text{ with dimensions } \begin{bmatrix} 1 \times 1 \\ (k-1) \times 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

290 where $a = 1, \dots, k$ and $\mathbf{b} = \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ where $a \notin \mathbf{b}$. This partitioning
 291 allows us to define block-wise mean and covariance as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_a \\ \boldsymbol{\mu}_b \end{bmatrix} \text{ with dimensions } \begin{bmatrix} 1 \times 1 \\ (k-1) \times 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

292 and

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{aa}^2 & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{ab} \\ \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{ba} & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{bb} \end{bmatrix} \text{ with dimensions } \begin{bmatrix} 1 \times 1 & 1 \times (k-1) \\ (k-1) \times 1 & (k-1) \times (k-1) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

293 Subsequently, we can derive the conditional distribution of any subset
 294 variable x_a , given the complementary vector \mathbf{x}_b . This conditional distribution
 295 conforms to a univariate normal distribution, characterized by:

$$X_a | \mathbf{X}_b \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_{a|b}, \sigma_{a|b}^2). \quad (14)$$

296 where $\mu_{a|b}$ denotes the conditional mean and $\sigma_{a|b}^2$ represents the condi-
 297 tional variance. These crucial parameters can be computed by applying the
 298 Schur complement as follows:

$$\sigma_{a|b}^2 = \sigma_{aa}^2 - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{ab} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{bb}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{ba}, \quad (15)$$

299 for the conditional variance $\sigma_{a|b}^2$, while the conditional mean, denoted as
 300 $\mu_{a|b}$, is determined by:

$$\mu_{a|b} = \mu_a + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{ab} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{bb}^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_b - \boldsymbol{\mu}_b). \quad (16)$$

301 The conditional variance $\sigma_{a|b}^2$ essentially represents the Schur complement
 302 of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{bb}$ within the overall covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$.

303 *2.5. Gaussian Anomaly Detection*

304 From a viewpoint of statistics, outliers are commonly denoted as values
 305 that significantly deviate from the mean. Under the assumption that the
 306 spatial and temporal characteristics of a system, observed over a moving
 307 window, can be suitably represented as normally distributed features, we
 308 assert that any anomaly can be identified as an outlier.

309 In empirical fields like machine learning, the three-sigma rule (3σ) pro-
 310 vides a framework for characterizing the region of a distribution within which
 311 normal values are expected to fall with high confidence. This rule renders
 312 approximately 0.265% of values in the distribution as anomalous.

313 The 3σ rule establishes the probability that any sample x_a of a random
 314 vector X falls within a given CDF over a semi-closed interval as the distance
 315 from the conditional mean $\mu_{a|\mathbf{b}}$ of 3 conditional variances $\sigma_{a|\mathbf{b}}^2$ and gives an
 316 approximate value of q as

$$q = P\{|x_a - \mu_{a|\mathbf{b}}| < 3\sigma_{a|\mathbf{b}}^2\} = 0.99735. \quad (17)$$

317 Utilizing a probabilistic model of normal behavior, we can determine
 318 threshold values x_l and x_u corresponding to the closed interval of the CDF
 319 where this probability is established. The inversion of Equation (10) facili-
 320 tates this calculation, yielding:

$$x_l = F((1 - P\{|x_a - \mu_{a|\mathbf{b}}| < 3\sigma_{a|\mathbf{b}}^2\}); \mu_{a|\mathbf{b}}, \sigma_{a|\mathbf{b}}^2)^{-1}, \quad (18)$$

321 for the lower limit, and

$$x_u = F((P\{|x_a - \mu_{a|\mathbf{b}}| < 3\sigma_{a|\mathbf{b}}^2\}); \mu_{a|\mathbf{b}}, \sigma_{a|\mathbf{b}}^2)^{-1}, \quad (19)$$

322 for the upper limit. These lower and upper limits together form vectors
 323 \mathbf{x}_l and \mathbf{x}_u , respectively, defining the region of normal system operation. This
 324 region is conceptualized as a hypercube in the feature space, with each di-
 325 mension bounded by the corresponding feature limits, as computed using
 326 Equations (18) and (19) for all $a = 1, \dots, k$; $\mathbf{b} = \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ where $a \notin \mathbf{b}$.
 327 The approximation of a confidence ellipse as a hypercube can be employed
 328 to represent the region of normal system operation for individual variables
 329 of a multivariate system, rendering it as an aid for visual representation.

330 The predicted state of the system, denoted as y_i , and the normality of
 331 signals $\mathbf{y}_{s,i}$ at time i are determined based on the maximum distance of
 332 observations from the center of the probabilistic density. The center of the

333 probabilistic density corresponds to the vector of conditional means $\mu_{a|\mathbf{b}}$ with
 334 respect to other features. The calculation of this distance involves the cumu-
 335 lative distribution function (CDF) of observations and conditional distribu-
 336 tions, as follows:

$$F(x_a; \mu_{a|\mathbf{b}}, \sigma_{a|\mathbf{b}}^2) : a = 1, \dots, k; \mathbf{b} = \{1, 2, \dots, k\} \text{ where } a \notin \mathbf{b}. \quad (20)$$

337 Subsequently, operation states of individual inputs are defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{y}_{s,i} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } T \leq (20) \\ 1 & \text{if } T > (20), \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

338 where T represents a threshold that distinguishes between normal signal
 339 measurement ($\mathbf{y}_{s,i} = 0$) and abnormal ($\mathbf{y}_{s,i} = 1$).

340 For the overall abnormality of the system, any anomaly in signals $\mathbf{y}_{s,i}$ is
 341 considered, resulting in:

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \in \mathbf{y}_{s,i} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

342 defining the discrimination boundary between system operation where
 343 $y_i = 0$ indicates normal system operation, and $y_i = 1$ indicates anomalous
 344 operation.

345 2.6. Anomaly Definition

346 This subsection provides an overview of the definition of anomalies in
 347 data analysis and their categorization, setting conventions for this paper.

348 In the realm of data analysis, anomalies are conspicuous deviations from
 349 the anticipated patterns within a dataset. Traditionally, the task of anomaly
 350 detection has relied upon unsupervised methodologies, wherein the identifi-
 351 cation of "outliers" entails the comparison of data points in both temporal
 352 and spatial contexts. This approach, often referred to as point-wise anomaly
 353 detection, classifies a data point as an anomaly when it exhibits significant
 354 dissimilarity from its neighboring data points (Iglesias Vázquez et al., 2023).

355 The concept of point anomalies, influenced by factors such as temporal
 356 and spatial aspects, can be further categorized into conditional and contex-
 357 tual anomalies (Ruff et al., 2021).

358 Nevertheless, this conventional method may not be suitable for scenarios
 359 characterized by collective anomalies, where clusters of abnormal data points

360 coexist. A more pragmatic approach defines anomalies as deviations from
361 established "normal" patterns, resembling the principles of semi-supervised
362 learning. Change point detection, in a similar vein, can be regarded as a
363 relative approach that takes into account the varying dynamics of changes,
364 whether they occur gradually or abruptly (Iglesias Vázquez et al., 2023).

365 It is imperative to recognize that the interpretation of anomalies, outliers,
366 and novelties can vary upon the application. Anomalies typically garner
367 significant attention, while outliers are often treated as undesirable noise
368 and are typically excluded during data preprocessing. Novelties, on the other
369 hand, signify new observations that necessitate model updates to adapt to
370 an evolving environment (Ruff et al., 2021).

371 Notwithstanding the differences in terminology, methods employed for the
372 identification of data points residing in low-probability regions, irrespective of
373 whether they are referred to as "anomaly detection," "outlier detection," or
374 "novelty detection," share fundamental similarities (Iglesias Vázquez et al.,
375 2023).

376 For visual clarity, Figure 2 illustrates the differences between point anom-
377 alies, collective anomalies, and change points.

Figure 2: Illustration of sample scenarios of point anomaly (measurement with significant dissimilarity), collective anomaly (cluster of abnormal points), and change point (initial sequence of changed operation) detection.

378 **3. Adaptive Anomaly Detection and Interpretation Framework**

379 In this section, we present an adaptive and interpretable detection frame-
380 work (AID) designed for SCADA-based industrial systems with streaming
381 IoT devices. Our approach is rooted in the foundational concepts discussed
382 in Preliminaries 2. We systematically leverage these theoretical building
383 blocks to introduce our method in a coherent manner.

384 Our approach begins by modeling the system as a dynamic multivariate
385 normal distribution, allowing it to effectively handle pervasive nonstationary
386 effects and interactions that impact industrial processes. We address several
387 critical factors, such as change points, concept drift, and seasonal effects.
388 Our primary contribution is the integration of an adaptable self-supervised
389 system with root cause identification and dynamic operating limits setting.
390 This unique combination empowers our online statistical model to diagnose
391 anomalies through three distinct mechanisms.

392 Firstly, we employ conditional probability calculations to assess the nor-
393 mality of the system’s operating conditions. This step ensures that our
394 method identifies outliers within individual signal measurements and inter-
395 prets the root causes of anomalies, facilitating faster and more precise diag-
396 noses. Secondly, we detect abrupt changes due to concept drift, serving for
397 faster adaptation to new operating conditions without human intervention.
398 Thirdly, we harness interpretability as a tool to establish dynamic operating
399 limits. These adaptive limits enable our framework to seamlessly integrate
400 with existing SCADA-based infrastructure, a substantial advantage over ex-
401 isting solutions.

402 We have structured the subsequent sections to delve into the details of our
403 proposed methodology by the logical flow of data. The upcoming subsection
404 will cover the anomaly detection mechanism, followed by sections on online
405 training and adaptation. The next subsection will describe dynamic operat-
406 ing limits setting, followed by diagnostic capabilities. Lastly, we describe how
407 those parts converge into a diagnostic tool. For a schematic representation of
408 our proposed method, with a highlighted subsection attribution, please refer
409 to Figure 3. For a concise technical representation of our proposed method,
410 please refer to Algorithm 1.

411 *3.1. Online detection*

412 In the online detection phase, AID distinguishes between normal and
413 anomalous observations based on the model of the system’s normal behavior.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the proposed method AID with parameter initialization. Colored boxes represent steps described within the subsection.

414 The detection pipeline is event-triggered upon the arrival of a new set of
 415 measurements.

416 To initiate the process, AID computes the properties of the conditional
 417 distribution based on the current observations given the dynamic joint normal
 418 distribution. These calculations are performed for each element of the
 419 process observation vector \mathbf{x}_i at time instance i . Specifically, we calculate the
 420 conditional mean using (16) and the conditional variance using (15) for ele-
 421 ments of \mathbf{x}_i . These computations yield univariate conditional distributions
 422 for individual signals and features. These conditional distributions play a
 423 crucial role in assessing the abnormality of signals and features concerning
 424 their relationships with other elements of \mathbf{x}_i . Consequently, AID inherently
 425 considers the interactions between input signals and features.

426 The determination of anomalous behavior is influenced by the param-
 427 eter T , which is a user-defined hyperparameter representing a probabilistic
 428 threshold that sets the boundary between normal and anomalous behavior.
 429 Details regarding the selection of an appropriate value for T are discussed
 430 in Subsection 3.5. Whenever an anomaly is detected within one of the sig-
 431 nals or features, it triggers an alert regarding the overall system’s anomalous
 432 behavior, as described in (22). Nevertheless, individual determinations of

433 anomalies serve as a diagnostic tool for isolating the root causes of anoma-
 434 lies, as further discussed in Subsection 3.4.

435 The proposed mechanism is applicable to both point anomalies and col-
 436 lective anomalies. In the case of collective anomalies, their duration and
 437 deviation may serve as precursors to concept drift in the system. To iden-
 438 tify concept drift, we introduce a parameter adaptation period t_a . Given
 439 the predicted system anomaly state from (22) as y_i over a window of past
 440 observations $\mathbf{y}_i = \{y_{i-t_a}, \dots, y_i\}$ bounded by t_a , the following test determines
 441 anticipated change points:

$$\frac{\sum_{y \in \mathbf{y}_i} y}{n(\mathbf{y}_i)} > T. \quad (23)$$

442 Here, $n(\mathbf{y}_i)$ denotes the dimensionality of \mathbf{y}_i . The logic behind (23) is
 443 that over an adaptation period t_a , change points can be distinguished from
 444 collective anomalies and point anomalies due to their minimum duration,
 445 while T allows for some overlap with previous normal conditions.

446 Our framework anticipates unexpected novel behavior, including non-
 447 uniformities in sampling. Assuming that the distribution of sampling times
 448 remains stable over the long term, we can employ equivalent steps on the
 449 observed time between samples to discriminate signal loss from long-term
 450 anomalous network events.

451 3.2. Online learning

452 AID’s training process follows an incremental self-learning approach, al-
 453 lowing for online model updates as new samples arrive. Self-learning, in this
 454 context, focuses on selecting only relevant data for training to maintain the
 455 model’s long-term relevancy and stability. This approach proves particularly
 456 valuable in handling streaming data, where human supervision can intro-
 457 duce significant computational delays, affecting response time in a sequential
 458 setting.

459 In online anomaly detector training, regardless of the type of supervi-
 460 sion, the learning is typically built upon observations of the normal state.
 461 We introduce a grace period denoted as t_g to enable model calibration in
 462 the initial stages after deployment. During this period, when normality in
 463 samples is expected, the model learns from all observations. Subsequently,
 464 self-supervised and unsupervised detectors are expected to make autonomous
 465 decisions.

466 However, in the case of industrial systems, the drifts in the concept might
467 often render the normal state anomalous, slowing down or preventing adap-
468 tation completely. This is particularly true for the case of seasonal effects,
469 where the system is expected to operate in a different mode for a certain
470 period of time. To address this issue, AID’s adaptation incorporates two
471 self-supervised mechanisms.

472 Firstly, the model is updated if the observation at time instance i is
473 marked normal in the detection phase. In the case of a dynamic multivariate
474 probability distribution, the updated parameters are $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i$ at time in-
475 stance i . Update of the mean vector $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ and covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i$ is governed
476 by Welford’s online algorithm using equation (2) and (4) respectively. Sam-
477 ples beyond the expiration period t_e , discussed further in Subsection 3.5, are
478 disregarded during the second pass. The effect of expired samples is reverted
479 using inverse Welford’s algorithm for mean (6) and variance (7), accessing the
480 data in the bounded internal buffer. For more details, refer to Subsection 2.2.

481 The second mechanism, which enables adaptation to anomalous samples,
482 relies on changepoint detection. This mechanism operates under the as-
483 sumption that detected changepoints represent new operational states with
484 limited overlap with the previous ones, as specified in Equation 23. It facili-
485 tates rapid adaptation to evolving data patterns without the need for human
486 intervention. The selection of the adaptation period t_a , as discussed further
487 in Subsection 3.5, is thus crucial for determining the speed of adaptation or
488 the potential mitigation of the second adaptation mechanism.

489 To anticipate potential deviations from sampling uniformity, we calculate
490 the cumulative distribution function (CDF) over the univariate normal dis-
491 tribution of sampling. We operate under the assumption that, over the long
492 term, the distribution of sampling times remains stable, employing a one-
493 pass update mechanism of (2) and (4), for efficiency. To proactively detect
494 subtle changes in sampling patterns, self-supervised learning is employed,
495 leveraging anomalies weighted by the deviation from $(1 - F(x_i; \mu, \sigma^2))$ for
496 training.

497 3.3. *Dynamic limits acquisition*

498 As we wrote in the subsection 1.4 Practical Impact, the monitoring mech-
499 anisms of SCADA readily depend on the upper and lower operating limits
500 of individual parameters of the system. In the case of industrial systems,
501 these limits are often defined by the sensor’s designed limits and the sys-
502 tem dynamics. These limits are typically static and do not account for the

503 dynamically changing conditions. Our proposed method AID is capable of
504 setting dynamic operating limits, thus allowing integration into the existing
505 SCADA-based infrastructure.

506 The threshold T applied on the dynamic multivariate normal distribution
507 creates a confidence hyperellipse at T probability level. Such a hyperellipse
508 would not allow to effectively bound individual signals as it depends on val-
509 ues that other jointly distributed variables take. Nevertheless, by computing
510 the conditional for process observation vector \mathbf{x}_i at time instance i , we can
511 compute the conditional density function for individual signals. By applying
512 threshold T on individual conditional probabilities, we establish a hyper-
513 cube defined by lower and upper threshold values, denoted as \mathbf{x}_l and \mathbf{x}_u ,
514 respectively. These thresholds are derived from (18) and (19), incorporating
515 updated model parameters. Lower and upper thresholds play a pivotal role
516 as dynamic operating limits. They may be used as an addition to static oper-
517 ating limits used by monitoring systems in SCADA, accounting for spatial
518 factors, such as multipoint measurements, temporal factors, such as aging,
519 and actual environmental conditions that influence sensor operation. More-
520 over, any violation of the limits is also detected as an anomaly.

521 *3.4. Diagnostics*

522 One of the crucial aspects of diagnostics is root cause isolation. Using the
523 ability to detect anomalies in individual signals and features, AID is capable
524 of isolating the root cause of anomalies with consideration of their mutual
525 relationships. This is achieved by computing the conditional probability of
526 individual signals and features given the rest of the process observation vector
527 \mathbf{x}_i at time instance i . The dynamic process limits further enhance the diagno-
528 sis by providing the context of the anomaly, including the extent of deviation
529 from normal operation and the direction of the deviation. The proposed di-
530 agnostic mechanism is particularly useful in the case of collective anomalies,
531 where the unified direction of deviations is expected. AID's interpretability is
532 an asset for domain experts to understand why certain anomalies are flagged
533 and enables operators to assess the system's state by visualizing limits and
534 deviations, thus detecting the speed at which the process variable approaches
535 the limits before an anomaly occurs.

536 *3.5. Model Parameters Initialization*

537 The model initialization is governed by defining two required hyperpa-
538 rameters of the model: the expiration period (t_e) and the threshold (T). The

539 expiration period determines the window size for time-rolling computations,
540 impacting the proportion of outliers within a given timeframe and directly in-
541 fluencing the relaxation (with a longer expiration period) or tightening (with
542 a shorter expiration period) of dynamic signal limits. Additionally, we intro-
543 duce a grace period t_g , which defaults to *uite*, allowing for model calibration.
544 During this grace period, system anomalies are not flagged to prevent false
545 positives and speed up self-supervised learning, introduced in Subsection 3.2.
546 t_g can take any value smaller than *uite*, if the detection must be delivered fast
547 after intergration. The length of the expiration period inversely correlates
548 with the model’s ability to adapt to sudden changes. The adaptation and
549 detection of significant drifts in the data-generating process, such as changes
550 in central tendency, is managed through the adaptation period t_a . A shorter
551 t_a results in faster adaptation to new operating conditions, while making the
552 system vulnerable to prolonged collective anomalies. A longer t_a results in
553 slower adaptation to significantly deviating new operations, but allows longer
554 alerts regarding collective anomalies. In most cases, $t_a = 1/4t_e$ offers optimal
555 performance.

556 As a general rule of thumb, expiration period t_e should be determined
557 based on the slowest observed dynamics within the multivariate system. The
558 threshold T defaults to the three-sigma probability of q in (17). Adjusting
559 this threshold can fine-tune the trade-off between precision and recall. A
560 lower threshold boosts recall but may lower precision, while a higher thresh-
561 old enhances precision at the cost of recall. We recommend starting with
562 the default values of other parameters and making adjustments based on
563 real-time model performance, as the model’s interpretability can reduce the
564 time and effort required for fine-tuning. The presence of one non-default
565 interpretable hyperparameter facilitates quick adaptation of AID in a broad
566 range of use cases.

Algorithm 1 Online Detection and Identification Workflow

Input: expiration period t_e

Output: system anomaly y_i , signal anomalies $\mathbf{y}_{s,i}$, sampling anomaly $y_{t,i}$,
change-point $y_{c,i}$, lower thresholds $\mathbf{x}_{l,i}$, upper thresholds $\mathbf{x}_{u,i}$,

Initialisation :

1: $i \leftarrow 1$; $n \leftarrow 1$; $T \leftarrow (17)$; $\boldsymbol{\mu} \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_0$; $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \leftarrow \mathbf{1}_{k \times k}$; $\mu_t \leftarrow 0$; $\sigma_t^2 \leftarrow 1$;

2: compute $F(\mathbf{x}_0; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$ using algorithm in Genz (2000);

LOOP Process

3: **loop**

4: $\mathbf{x}_i, t_i \leftarrow \text{RECEIVE}()$;

5: $\mathbf{y}_{s,i} \leftarrow \text{PREDICT}(\mathbf{x}_i, T)$ using (21);

6: $y_i \leftarrow \text{PREDICT}(\mathbf{y}_{s,i})$ using (22);

7: $\mathbf{x}_{l,i}, \mathbf{x}_{u,i} \leftarrow \text{GET}(T, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$ using (18), (19);

8: $y_{t,i} \leftarrow \text{PREDICT}(t_i - t_{i-1})$ using (21);

9: $\mu_t, \sigma_t^2 \leftarrow \text{UPDATE}(t_i - t_{i-1}, \mu_t, \sigma_t^2)$ using (2), (4);

10: **if** (22) = 0 **or** (23) **then**

11: $\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \leftarrow \text{UPDATE}(\mathbf{x}_i, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}, n)$ using (2), (4);

12: **if** (23) **then**

13: $y_{c,i} \leftarrow 1$;

14: **else**

15: $y_{c,i} \leftarrow 0$;

16: **end if**

17: $n \leftarrow n + 1$;

18: **for** \mathbf{x}_{i-t_e} **do**

19: $\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \leftarrow \text{REVERT}(\mathbf{x}_{i-t_e}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}, n)$ using (6), (7);

20: $n \leftarrow n - 1$;

21: **end for**

22: **end if**

23: $i \leftarrow i + 1$;

24: **end loop**

567 4. Case Study

568 This section presents two case studies on real industrial-scale energy stor-
569 ages and a real data benchmark to demonstrate the effectiveness and appli-
570 cability of our proposed approach. We investigate the properties and perfor-
571 mance of the approach using signals from IoT devices in an energy system
572 and streamed benchmark system data. The successful deployment demon-
573 strates that this approach is suitable for existing industrial systems utilizing
574 IoT data streams on top of well-established SCADA systems.

575 4.1. Battery Energy Storage System TERRA

576 In the first case study, we demonstrate our proposed method on real
577 industrial-scale battery energy storage system (BESS) TERRA, depicted in
578 Fig 4. TERRA has an installed capacity of 151 kWh distributed among 10
579 modules with 20 Li-ion NMC cells. The Inverter’s nominal power is 100 kW.
580 The TERRA reports measurements of State of Charge (SoC), supply/draw
581 energy set-points, and inner temperature, at 6 positions (channels) of each
582 battery module. A substantial size of the system, which is 2.4x2.4x1.2m
583 (HxWxD), requires a proper cooling mechanism. The cooling is handled by
584 forced air from the HVAC system and inner fans, while the fire safety system
585 is passive. Tight battery temperature control is needed to optimize perfor-
586 mance and maximize the safety and battery’s lifespan. Identifying anomalous
587 events and removal of corrupted data might yield significant improvement in
588 the process control level and increase the reliability and stability of the sys-
589 tem.

590 The AID is integrated into the existing software infrastructure of the
591 system, allowing detection and diagnosis of the system using streamed IoT
592 data. Here we replay a 9-day stream of historical measurements of the device,
593 to demonstrate key features of AID.

594 For demonstration purposes, the expiration period t_e is set to 4 days, as
595 the system is expected to adapt to the new behavior, due to the transfer of
596 the module to the outside. The grace period was reduced to 1 day, to observe
597 the reaction to concept drift. The threshold T is set to 3.5σ to reduce the
598 number of alarms. The frequency will be higher as the detector is protected
599 and self-supervised. The adaptation period t_a is changed to 3 hours as this
600 is the time constant of the temperature to the unit change of supply/draw
601 power demand.

Figure 4: Photograph of the actual studied TERRA energy storage unit with open doors (left), and closed doors (right).

602 Figure 5 depicts the average cell temperature measurement of the TERRA
603 for all 10 modules. The data are normalized to the range $[0, 1]$ to protect
604 the sensitive business value. The light red area represents the region out of
605 dynamic operating limits as provided by AID. On 7th March 2022, the system
606 was relocated from the inside of the building to the outside power socket. The
607 system was expected to adapt to the new behavior within 4 days as specified
608 by t_e . Nevertheless, due to the protection of the model from learning the
609 anomalous data, the new behavior could not be captured as the system was
610 not operating within the safe limits. The adaptation started three days later,
611 as only some of the measurements within the safe region after transfer were
612 learned. Therefore, the importance of self-supervised adaptation to changes
613 in data is crucial. As we can see, the change points detection according to
614 (23) alerted such change shortly after the TERRA was connected to a data
615 broker, while the length of the adaptation period enabled discrimination from
616 collective anomaly.

617 In Figure 6 we depict the same measurement with a changepoint adap-
618 tation mechanism in place. The mechanism speeds up the adaptation to the
619 new behavior, as the system is allowed to learn from anomalous data when
620 they represent the changed behavior. The adaptation took approximately 6
621 times shorter.

622 The default sampling rate of the incoming signal measurements is 1
623 minute. However, network communication of the IoT devices is prone to

Figure 5: Detection of anomalies using model **without** adaptation to change points in normalized average cell temperature of TERRA observed over nine days (blue line). The model alerts anomalies (red dots) for approximately three days. The dynamic operating limits (light red area), given by the model without adaptation to change points, are stagnant during the period of detected change point (orange bars), which is triggered t_a hours after anomaly is alerted. The adaptation of the model to novel behavior starts as the t_e is approached.

Figure 6: Detection of anomalies using model **with** adaptation to change points over the same historical measurement as in Figure 5. The change point is detected t_a hours after the anomaly is alerted, triggering adaptation to changed behavior more than two days sooner, compared to model **without** adaptation to change points in Figure 5. The adaptation is reflected in changes in dynamic operating limits. The system alerts anomalies for approximately 10 hours.

624 packet dropout, which results in unexpected non-uniformities in sampling
625 from the perspective of the SCADA system. The transfer of TERRA was
626 accompanied by the disconnection of IoT sensors from the data broker which
627 might be considered an anomaly. The system can detect such anomalies as
628 well, as depicted in Figure 7. Along with known disconnection, the system
629 alerted two more non-uniformities of shorter extend, scaled in the figure for
630 better visibility. The short loss of signal was caused by the packet drop,
631 as it impacted only a few consecutive measurements. Various confidence levels
632 could be used to further analyze and map potential causes to the duration
633 of the outage.

Figure 7: Depiction of accompanying task of sampling anomaly detection (green bars) for model **with** adaptation to change points from Figure 6. Zoomed areas focus on short events of abnormal sampling detected by AID. The second zoomed area also highlights faulty measurements, which the system marked as point anomalies (red dots in the main figure area). The scaling in Figure 5 and Figure 6 for visibility rendered this fault out of the axis.

634 Lastly, we want to acknowledge the outlier, left uncaptured due to in-
635 creased variance of the distribution in a period of adaptation. Observing
636 multiple variables, where some might be influenced less by the change in be-
637 havior, might be beneficial in such cases. The industrial partner provided a
638 physics-based model of the battery module temperature, defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
T_{\text{bat},i+1} = & T_{\text{bat},i} + T_s(q_{\text{fan}} V_{\text{b,max}} \rho c_p (T_{\text{out}} - T_{\text{bat},i}) + V_{\text{c,max}} q_{\text{circ.fan}} \rho c_p T_{\text{bat},i} \\
& + q_{\text{circ.fan}} (P_{\text{cool}} q_{\text{cool}} P_{\text{heat}} q_{\text{heat}}) + c_{\text{scale}} Q_{\text{bat}} + q_{\text{inner fans}} \\
& - (V_{\text{b,max}} q_{\text{fan}} V_{\text{c,max}} q_{\text{circ.fan}}) \rho c_p T_{\text{bat},i}) / (m_{\text{bat}} c_{p,b})
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

639 When combined with an averaged measurement of battery module tem-
640 perature, we could compute the difference between real and predicted tem-
641 perature. Such deviation can be useful in detecting unexpected patterns in
642 temperature due to the impact of external disturbance and aging. Neverthe-
643 less, it may be inaccurate as the physics-based model is simplified and does
644 not account for spatial aspects, like temperature gradients as well as different
645 dynamic effects of charging and discharging on temperature. For instance,
646 in Fig. 4 during the first two days we see, that the cooling dynamic is not
647 captured well, resulting in a subtle positive difference between average cell
648 temperature and the temperature predicted by the model. In combination
649 with the raw measured average of the temperature, the AID captures the
650 outlier on 9th March which could not be captured in a univariate setting.
651 The physics-based model exposes temporal aspects of the behavior as it con-
652 siders the dynamics of its inputs. The rapid increase in temperature w.r.t
653 the modeled dynamics due to environmental conditions will draw a sharp
654 positive peak in the difference between the real and predicted temperature,
655 which will slowly vanish. Based on the significance of the deviation, the peak
656 will be notified as a single-point anomaly or collective anomaly.

657 This case study demonstrated AID’s effectiveness within the context of
658 the energy storage system, specifically the TERRA system. The AID system
659 exhibited adaptability to changes in the operational environment, contribut-
660 ing to its versatility and robustness. Additionally, it facilitated the establish-
661 ment of dynamic operating limits for SCADA systems, considering context
662 of the device such as environmental conditions or aging. Furthermore, the
663 AID system showcased its capability to operate with a physics-based model,
664 enhancing the precision of anomaly detection processes. This highlights the
665 potential of AID as a valuable tool within complex industrial systems. The
666 validity of our proposed approach was verified by our industrial partner, who
667 confirmed that the detected anomalies were indeed caused by the aforemen-
668 tioned events.

669 *4.2. Kokam Battery Module*

670 A second case study presents temperature profile monitoring of individual
671 modules of battery pack TERRA deployed at the premises of the end user.
672 During the operation, a hardware fault of module’s 9 cooling fan occurred on
673 23rd August 2023 at 17:12:30. Our industrial partner was interested in find-
674 ing out, whether such an event could be captured by an anomaly detection
675 system. Each of the 10 modules, embodies 20 cells measured by 6 spatially

Figure 8: Time series of TERRA measurements observed over 9 days (blue line). The y-axis renders the average temperature of all cells and modules after the normalization to the range of $[0, 1]$. The light red area represents an area out of dynamic operating limits for individual signals. Observations out of the limits are marked by a red dot. Orange bars represent the times, at which changepoints were detected. Green bars represent periods where sampling anomaly was alerted. Red bars denote the period where any of the signals contained anomaly. Grace period is grayed out.

676 distributed sensors as shown in Figure 9. The measurements are sent in 30-
 677 second intervals and processed in a streamed manner by SCADA. With the
 678 availability of the temperature profiles for all the modules, we computed the
 679 deviation of the observed value from the average of all the modules' temper-
 680 ature measurements. The ground truth information about the fan fault was
 681 provided to the best of the operator's knowledge. However, this information
 682 serves for evaluation only, as the system operates in a self-supervised manner.

Figure 9: Module 9 with 20 cells and 6 sensors measuring the temperature at each 4th cell.

683 Our anomaly detection system was, in this case, initialized for the op-
 684 eration in production. The expiration period of 7 days, allowed the system
 685 to adapt to weekly seasonality due to the usage of the battery following
 686 work week. The grace period was kept at the default value, equal to t_e . The
 687 threshold value was shifted to a 4 sigma value of 99.977% which makes the the
 688 frequency of anomalous events approximately once a week given 30-second
 689 sampling. The adaptation period was held constant as the deployed system
 690 is not expected to change its behavior dramatically on a daily basis.

691 In Figure 10 we observe 4 days of operation around the period of fan
 692 fault occurrence. The deviations between the observed temperature mea-
 693 sured by channels of module 9 and the average temperature of all modules
 694 are displayed. The dynamic operating limits tightly envelop temperatures
 695 measured by the sensors in the middle of the module (refer to Figure 9),

696 while measurements at both sides deviate more due to the proximity to the
697 walls and sources of disturbance. We observed multiple alarms raised by var-
698 ious channels individually before the fan fault. These anomalies, while not
699 addressed here further, could be subjects of interest for further investigation
700 by system operators. Meanwhile, the fan fault at the center of our focus is
701 alarmed based on three measurements, namely channels 1, 2, and 3. From
702 the zoomed views, we can observe a sharp increase in the temperature devia-
703 tion. The alarm is on until 24th August at noon, when significant fluctuations
704 vanish followed by temporary settling of the temperature. On 25th August
705 at 11:21, increased temperature fluctuations are followed by an increase of
706 temperature similar to the initial one. AID alerts this fault again based on
707 measurements by channels 1, 2, and 3.

708 Time series of TERRA measurements observed over 9 days (blue line).
709 The y-axis renders the average temperature of all cells and modules after the
710 normalization to the range of $[0, 1]$. The light red area represents an area out
711 of dynamic operating limits for individual signals. Observations out of the
712 limits are marked by a red dot. Orange bars represent the times, at which
713 changepoints were detected. Green bars represent periods where sampling
714 anomaly was alerted. Red bars denote the period where any of the signals
715 contained anomaly. Grace period is grayed out.

716 Interestingly, during the presence of a fault in the fan, two more peri-
717 ods where the fan started operating again followed as depicted in Figure 11.
718 Periods of operation were interrupted again on 27th and 28th August respec-
719 tively in the early morning hours. In both of the cases, AID detected the
720 presence of the fault at the moment of occurrence. In the first case, channel
721 3 reported an anomaly slightly before the increase in temperature, due to
722 abnormal fluctuation happening prior to faults.

723 This case study demonstrates the effectiveness of the AID framework in
724 identifying hardware faults within the context of energy storage systems. It
725 showcases the system’s ability to harness spatially distributed sensors that
726 measure the same process variable. The AID system successfully pinpointed
727 a fault in a cooling fan during real-world production operations, underlining
728 its practical utility and its relevance in enhancing the safety of energy storage
729 systems. Furthermore, the incorporation of adaptation mechanisms ensures
730 that the system can be deployed over extended periods without necessitating
731 resource-intensive retraining. Additionally, the concept of dynamic operating
732 limits introduced in this study holds promise for integration with Supervisory
733 Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) monitoring systems, enabling proac-

Figure 10: Time series of battery module 9 measurements (blue line). The y-axis renders the normalized deviations of temperature from the average of all modules. Signal anomalies are marked as red dots. The light red area represents an area out of dynamic operating limits. True fan faults are marked by purple bars. Green bars represent the times of changepoint detection. Red bars denote the period where any signal anomaly.

Figure 11: Time series of battery module 9 measurements (blue line). The y-axis renders the normalized deviations of temperature from an average of all modules. Signal anomalies are marked as red dots. The light red area represents an area out of dynamic operating limits. True fan faults are marked by purple bars. Green bars represent the times of changepoint detection. Red bars denote the period where any of the signals contained an anomaly.

734 tive responses in situations where human life, equipment, or the environment
735 may be at risk.

736 *4.3. Real Data Benchmark*

737 The benchmarking comparison in this subsection evaluates the AID frame-
738 work against adaptive unsupervised detection methods, specifically One-
739 Class Support Vector Machine (OC-SVM) and Half-Space Trees (HS-Trees).
740 These methods are widely recognized for their iterative learning capabilities
741 on multivariate time-series data, making them suitable for anomaly detection
742 in dynamic systems, as previously discussed in the Introduction 1.3.

743 The comparison is based on the Skoltech Anomaly Benchmark (SKAB)
744 dataset, a real-world dataset with annotated labels distinguishing between
745 anomalous and normal observations (Katser and Kozitsin, 2020). SKAB
746 is used for this purpose, as no established benchmarking multivariate data
747 were found regarding energy storage systems similar to the ones studied in
748 Subsection 4.1 and Subsection 4.2. The SKAB dataset involves experiments
749 related to rotor imbalance, where various control actions and changes in
750 water volume are introduced to the system. It encompasses eight features
751 and exhibits both gradual and sudden drifts.

752 To ensure fairness in the benchmark, data preprocessing adheres to best
753 practices for each method. OC-SVM employs standard scaling, while HS-
754 Trees use normalization. Our proposed AID method requires no scaling.
755 Preprocessing is performed online, simulating a real production environment,
756 with running mean and variance for standard scaling and running peak-to-
757 peak distance for normalization, as supported by the online machine learning
758 library "river" (Montiel et al., 2021).

759 The optimal hyperparameters for both reference methods are found us-
760 ing Bayesian Optimization. Due to no further knowledge about the data
761 generating process, and equity in benchmark, the hyperparameters of our
762 proposed method were optimized using Bayesian Optimization as well. 20
763 steps of random exploration with 100 iterations of Bayesian Optimization
764 were used, increasing default values set in the Bayesian Optimization library,
765 to allow thorough exploration and increase the possibility of finding global
766 optima in each case (Nogueira, 2014). The hyperparameters are optimized
767 with the F1 score as a cost function first, to maximize both precision and
768 recall on anomalous samples.

769 As adaptation is required and anticipated within benchmark datasets,
770 the performance is evaluated iteratively, similarly to the operation after de-

771 ployment. The metric is updated with each new sample and its final value is
 772 used to drive Bayesian Optimization. The performance is evaluated using the
 773 best-performing model, found by Bayesian Optimization. The performance
 774 of the proposed method is evaluated on the same data as the models are
 775 optimized for.

776 Hyperparameter search ranges are specified, with values centered around
 777 default library values for OC-SVM and HS-Trees. The ranges are inten-
 778 tionally set wide to facilitate comprehensive exploration. The quantile filter
 779 threshold used in OC-SVM and HS-Trees aligns with the threshold used in
 780 AID. These hyperparameter ranges are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Hyperparameter Ranges for Detection Algorithms

Algorithm	Hyperparameters	Default	Ranges
AID	Threshold	0.99735	(0.85, 0.99994)
	t_e	-	(150, 10000)
	t_a	t_e	(50, 2000)
	t_g	t_e	(50, 1000)
OC-SVM	Threshold	-	(0.85, 0.99994)
	Learning Rate	0.01	(0.005, 0.02)
HS-Trees	Threshold	-	(0.85, 0.99994)
	N Trees	10	(0, 20)
	Max Height	8	(2, 14)
	Window Size	250	(100, 400)

781 The results for models optimized for the F1 score are summarized in Ta-
 782 ble 2, which includes precision, recall, F1 score, and average latency. Macro
 783 values are enclosed in brackets, representing the mean of the metric for both
 784 anomalies and normal data. A perfect detection achieves 100% in each met-
 785 ric except for the false positive rate (FAR), where a perfect detection attains
 786 0%. According to the Scoreboard for various algorithms on SKAB’s Kaggle
 787 page, all iterative approaches perform comparably to the batch-trained iso-
 788 lation forest and autoencoder, validating the optimization process. Notably,
 789 the proposed AID method outperforms both reference methods in terms of
 790 precision, recall, F1 score, area under curve, and false positive rate, despite
 791 having a 30-fold higher latency per sample. This highlights the scalability
 792 as a candidate for further development. Nevertheless, in this case, sampling
 793 of the benchmark data still offers enough time to deliver predictions with

794 sufficient frequency. Scalability analysis to number of features is presented
 795 in Subsection 4.4.

Table 2: Evaluation of models optimized for F1 score on SKAB dataset (Katser and Kozitsin, 2020). The best-performing model is highlighted in bold. Values in brackets represent macro values of the metric.

Algorithm	AID	HS-Trees	OC-SVM
Precision [%]	41 (59)	36 (51)	39 (54)
Recall [%]	80 (59)	74 (51)	63 (54)
F1 [%]	54 (53)	48 (44)	48 (52)
AUC [%]	59	51	54
Mean Rolling AUC [%]	57	50	53
FPR [%]	47	56	48
Avg. Latency [ms]	1.45	0.05	0.05

796 Optimal hyperparameters found during Bayesian Optimization are de-
 797 tailed in Table 3. None of the parameters are at the edge of the provided
 798 ranges, serving as necessary proof of ranges being broad enough. Never-
 799 theless, sufficient proof is not possible as multiple parameter ranges are not
 800 bounded by designed limits.

Table 3: Optimal hyperparameters of methods optimized for F1 score

Algorithm	Hyperparameters	Found
AID	Threshold	0.96442
	t_e	1136
	t_a	396
	t_g	546
OC-SVM	Threshold	0.86411
	Learning Rate	0.01956
HS-Trees	Threshold	0.99715
	N Trees	1
	Max Height	7
	Window Size	283

801 *4.4. Scalability Analysis*

802 We evaluate the scalability of the proposed method using temperature
 803 data from 10 battery modules with six temperature measurement points in
 804 the TERRA system. The data, sampled at 30-second intervals, are streamed
 805 to the AID system, which is initialized with parameters identical to those
 806 in Subsection 4.2. Processing the data in a streamed manner simulates a
 807 real production environment. Latency is measured as the time between the
 808 sample’s arrival and the prediction’s delivery, including model updates. This
 809 evaluation occurs in a containerized environment with a single core and 8 GB
 810 RAM. Latency measurement spans 20160 samples from 2023-08-21 to 2023-
 811 08-27, excluding all but one measurement made during the grace period of 1
 812 day. We analyze latency for both the detection task alone and the combined
 813 task of detection and establishing dynamic process limits. Table 4 presents
 814 statistical indicators of the results, while the accompanying violin plots in
 815 the Figure offer visual insights into latency distribution for varying numbers
 816 of features. The significantly smaller minimum latency is attributed to eval-
 817 uation during the grace period, where fewer computations are performed.
 818 The significantly higher maximum latency could be attributed to reverting
 819 the effect of multiple points after signal loss in time-series data occurs.

Table 4: Latency analysis of the proposed method AID with varying number of features.

Number of Features	Detection $\mu \pm \sigma$ (min, max) [ms]	Detection + Limits $\mu \pm \sigma$ (min, max) [ms]
1	0.37 ± 0.26 (0.05, 31.7)	0.63 ± 0.38 (0.23, 35.9)
10	2.25 ± 0.92 (0.10, 13.6)	5.24 ± 0.98 (0.80, 15.1)
20	5.46 ± 2.16 (0.26, 30.6)	14.7 ± 2.27 (1.10, 47.5)
30	10.9 ± 4.31 (0.52, 42.4)	34.3 ± 4.50 (2.59, 72.4)
40	20.7 ± 8.15 (0.89, 52.7)	69.5 ± 8.57 (2.84, 140)
50	97.3 ± 47.4 (1.36, 1010)	297 ± 59.4 (3.94, 1330)
60	142 ± 71.2 (1.95, 1640)	468 ± 111 (7.08, 3710)

820 **5. Conclusion**

821 In this paper, we demonstrate the capacity of adaptive conditional prob-
 822 ability distribution to model the normal operation of dynamic systems em-

Figure 12: Analysis of latency distribution of the proposed method AID. Violin plots depict the distribution of the latency for varying number of features, while horizontal bars show mean latency.

823 ploying streaming IoT data and isolate the root cause of anomalies. AID
824 dynamically adapts to non-stationarity by updating multivariate Gaussian
825 distribution parameters over time. Additionally, self-supervision enhances
826 the model by protecting it from the effects of outliers and increasing the
827 speed of adaptation in response to autonomously detected changes in oper-
828 ation.

829 Our statistical model isolates the root causes of anomalies as extreme
830 deviations from the conditional means vector, considering spatial and tem-
831 poral effects encoded in features, as demonstrated in our case studies. This
832 approach establishes the system’s operational state by analyzing the dis-
833 tribution of signal measurements, computing the distance from the mean
834 of conditional probability, and setting dynamic operating limits based on
835 multivariate distribution parameters. Additionally, the detector alerts for
836 non-uniform sampling due to packet drops and sensor malfunctions. These
837 adaptable limits can be seamlessly integrated into SCADA architecture, en-
838 hancing context awareness and enabling plug-and-play compatibility with
839 existing infrastructure.

840 The ability to detect and identify anomalies in the system, isolate the
841 root cause of anomaly to specific signal or feature, and identify signal losses
842 is shown in two case studies on data from operated industrial-scale energy
843 storages. These case studies highlight the model’s ability to adapt, diagnose
844 the root cause of anomalies, and leverage both physics-based models and
845 spatially distributed sensors. Unlike many anomaly detection approaches,
846 the proposed AID method does not require historical data or ground truth
847 information about anomalies, alleviating the general limitations of detection
848 methods employed in the energy industry.

849 The benchmark performed on industrial data indicates that our model
850 provides comparable results to other self-learning adaptable anomaly detec-
851 tion methods. This is an important property of our model, as it also allows
852 for root cause isolation.

853 AID represents a significant advancement in the safety and profitability
854 of evolving systems that utilize well-established SCADA architecture and
855 streaming IoT data. By providing dynamic operating limits, AID seamlessly
856 integrates with existing alarm mechanisms commonly employed in SCADA
857 systems. To the best of our knowledge, this study appears to be one of the
858 initial attempts to introduce a self-supervised approach for adaptive anomaly
859 detection and root cause isolation in SCADA-based systems utilizing IoT
860 data streams.

861 Future work on this method will include improvements to the change point
862 detection mechanism, reduction in latency for high-dimensional data, and
863 minimizing the false positive rate, which is a challenge for general plug-and-
864 play models. We will also explore the ability to operate with non-parametric
865 models, in contrast to Gaussian distribution.

866 **Additional information**

867 Our framework is openly accessible on GitHub at the following URL:
868 https://github.com/MarekWadinger/online_outlier_detection.

869 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

870 **Marek Wadinger:** Conceptualization; Data curation; Formal analysis;
871 Investigation; Methodology; Resources; Software; Validation; Visualization;
872 Writing - original draft; and Writing - review & editing. **Michal Kvasnica:**
873 Conceptualization; Funding acquisition; Project administration; Resources;
874 Supervision; Validation.

875 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

876 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial inter-
877 ests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work
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